

Figure S1. Full view of the six La Voulte-sur-Rhône fossil slabs included in this study. A: *Palaeopycnogonides gracilis* holotype MNHN.F.A52381 and specimen MNHN.F.A88072. B: *Palaeopycnogonides gracilis*, paratypes MNHN.F.A52382 and A52383, and specimens MNHN.F.A88073–A88078. C: *Palaeopycnogonides gracilis* paratype MNHN.F.A52384 (also includes *Palaeopycnogonides?* *gracilis?* hidden specimen MNHN.F.A88079). D: *Colossopantopodus boissinensis*, holotype MNHN.F.A52385. E: *Palaeoendeis elmii*, holotype MNHN.F.A49277. F: Pantopoda indet. specimen MNHN.F.A52386. Scales bars: 2cm (A, C-F); 5 cm (B). Pictures Noël Podevigne.

Figure S2. Different CT-scan slices of the trunk of *Palaeopycnogonides gracilis* Charbonnier, Vannier & Riou, 2007, holotype MNHN.F.A52381 (A–B) and paratype MNHN.F.A52384 (C–D) showing internal low density outline within the pyritized fossils. Images reconstructed from raw CT-scan data using the software ORS Dragonfly (build 2021.3.0.1087, Montreal, Canada). Scale bars: 5 mm.